

PAKISTAN A VICTIM OR PERPETRATOR OF TERRORISM: CONTENT ANALYSIS OF THE WORLD'S MOST FAMOUS MAGAZINES

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Abstract

Pakistan has been a part of the war on terrorism since the Soviet Union invasion of Afghanistan, followed by US war on terror. Despite its efforts Pakistan still struggles to get a positive image internationally. This paper is a qualitative study, using content analysis on three leading news magazines of the world to ascertain the image of Pakistan as portrayed in these magazines during the time period of Zarb-e-Azb operation (2014-2016). The quantitative analysis of the data showed that these magazines do not portray a positive image of Pakistan in front of the world. The study is significant to policy makers to take up the issue on high forums and bring in a change in this view.

INTRODUCTION

Since the Soviet Union invasion of Afghanistan, the Islamic Republic of Pakistan has been facing the consequences of Soviet war in multiple forms and shapes. One of the most consequential outcomes of this war has been terrorism in forms of extremism and violence (Hughes, 2008). After the Soviet invasion this curse of terrorism further spread like a plague around the world when the United States of America (USA) had to face deadly attacks on its soil on September 11, 2001 (9/11) and as a consequence attacked Afghanistan once again (Crawford, 2018). The attack by the United States of America once again dragged the Islamic Republic of Pakistan into an unending war with terrorists (Wienbaum & Hardwe, 2008). Pakistan has been operating as an ally of the USA against the war on terrorism, but its image internationally has been not impressive (Rashid,

2008). Pakistan has never enjoyed a positive image when it comes to war against terrorism. A major role in nurturing and portraying this image around the globe is because of the leading media houses. Media in its various forms that might be print or electronic has depicted Pakistan as a safe haven for terrorist to a wide array of audience.

Contrary to that Pakistan is experiencing a wave of terrorism for more than two decades that has a huge cost in economic (loss of \$130 billion) and human (more than 70,000 people killed) terms. Pakistan is a country that is experiencing violence in different shapes and forms may it be suicide attacks on public places, bombing on target places, or ethnic conflicts in Balochistan and Karachi (Saeed, Syed & Martin, 2014). Ahmed (2016) asserts that the inactions of stakeholders have led to the creation of many religious

and ethnic groups, hence increasing violent extremism in the country Javaid (2022) while explaining Pakistan's attempt to devise an inclusive strategy argues that deradicalization and counter-radicalization has always been two aspects of Pakistan's terrorism programs. However, despite such programs the question remains, whether military operations alone can be effective in eliminating the peril of radicalism, and improving Pakistan's image internationally. This raises the question what is Pakistan image internationally and how it is shaped through communication by international media houses.

There is a popular narrative by the USA that Pakistan has to do more as a partner in this war on terrorism (Jenkins & Godges, 2011). This narrative has created an image about the country that it is a facilitator or a perpetrator in terrorism. Before countering this narrative, it is imperative to analysis if this assumption is correct or not.

The purpose of this qualitative research is to ascertain the image of Pakistan either as a victim or as a perpetrator of terrorism by doing a content analysis of the world three leading magazines, Newsweek, Time and the Economist (Kracauer, 2022). The basis of selection of these magazines is that they are widely read and distributed around the world. The study will cover the time period from 2014 to 2016 as this was the time when the military operation Zarb-e-Azb was in full throttle and it was the time when Pakistan showed the world it has done the most in this war. Javaid (2020) claims that during this operation Pakistan was able to break the vicious cycle of extremism and violence by scarifying almost 500 of soldiers and killing 3,500 militants. Besides that, more than one million people were internally displaced because of this operation (Hameed, 2015). Javaid (2020) claims that the country was able to destroy almost 1000 hideouts of militants and forcing them out of Pakistan. While Pakistan was achieving so much in the war against terrorism, we must find out how the leading international media houses were portraying Pakistan to the world. For this purpose, a content analysis of Newsweek, Time and the Economist magazines is conducted in this study.

I. Literature Review

The literature review is divided into three themes to create a clarity of arguments. The first theme will discuss how Pakistan is theorized and discussed in relation with the war on terrorism. The second theme explains the role of communication in image creation and how it creates or alter perception of people and countries. The Final part explains how media framing is practice by powerful media houses and how it used to create a desired perception in minds of people.

a. Pakistan and Terrorism

The Islamic Republic of Pakistan and terrorism have been linked to one another since the Afghan war against the Soviet Union since the 1980s and 1990s (Maley, 2020). During the Soviet invasion when Pakistan was helping the USA and its allies it was considered as a hero and vital partner by the world (Malik & He, 2019). During that the Afghan fighters were labelled as *Mujahidins*. Siraj (2006) explains that the same Afghan war led to the birth of the Taliban and Talibanization which is now considered to be the deadliest weapon since the inception of the Islamic State for Iraq and Syria (ISIS) The same Mujahids turned into terrorists once they challenged the mighty USA. During the Soviet war Pakistan sheltered millions of displaced Afghans and was considered a magnanimous country but after 9/11 we were blamed for harbouring them (Yousafzai, 2021).

The second phase of terrorism that came upon the state of Pakistan was when the attacks of 9/11 were carried out in the United States of America. Rabbi (2012) asserts that these attacks on the United States of America placed Pakistan in the most vulnerable situation as it had to decide either to side with USA or not. Even though Pakistan became an ally of the West against terrorism, it is still seen as a country that is nurturing terrorism. After joining the West's war on terrorism Pakistan suffered the most from the terrorist activities compare to any other partner. They not only faced losses in terms of human casualties but also economically and socially (Rabbi, 2012) Despite all these facts from the West still don't consider Pakistan their partner (Fair, 2012).

Al-Qaeda is the name that brought upon the wrath of terrorism to the whole world. It is the leadership of Al-Qaeda that is believed to control and carry out most of terrorist activities globally. Al-Qaeda and

many other banned terrorist groups have been very active in the region of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan since the inception of “War on Terrorism,” a name given to US envision by the western media (Siraj, 2006). One of the leading factors for their activities in Pakistan was due to the porous nature border with Afghanistan (Ahmed, Khan & Fayaz, 2022). Beside that the world must not forget that Pakistan is giving shelter to millions of Afghan refugees and these militants blend in them to escape the eyes of law enforcing agencies (Borthakur, 2017) Despite these shortcomings the country is still persistence to fight terrorism and has employed different approaches. Few of these approaches have been successful and few have faced failures, but it doesn't mean that the country is not trying.

The Top-Down approach for tackling extremism has not been fruitful in Pakistan. As a result, different plans such as National Action Plan (NAP) to control violence in the country has not been sustainable. The stakeholders that really matter, such as, the middle and lower-level bureaucrats whose opinions must be listened to are missing from all strategies implemented so far. Despite these shortcomings the action plan was not a total failure. The NAP's 20 points have achieved varying levels of success in past many years (Zahid, 2016). Such as the Karachi operation is considered as a success of NAP, the city was on the brink of failure but after the operation things changed dramatically. FATA region merger in Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa is another milestone of NAP. The region due to its remoteness and underdevelopment was an easy target for terrorist outfits but after the merger things are changing for good in the region. Finally, substantial actions have been taken to restraint terror financing in the country. However, on the other hand there is evidence inferring that the plan was not that successful in countering violent extremism (Wahab, 2021). Sahill (2018) claims that one the main area of failure is the online glorification of extremism and fake news management. With the help of social media and strategic communication terrorists were able to recruit many supporters. Apart from this hate speeches were circulated through social media without any effective check from the authorities (Abid, Shami & Ashfaq, 2021).

Khan and Saeed (2018) explain that keeping in view the importance of social media communication and

its implications on life of people, NACTA had launched applications such as Chaukas and Tatheer. Through them suspicious activities on social media were informed to authorities by public. All these activities by the government shows their seriousness to tackle terrorism. However, there is more to do on sphere communication. It is further argued how social media communication was used by extremists to increase militancy by sharing hate material directly to public (Abid, Shami & Ashfaq, 2021). It is pertinent to mention that tackling terrorism promotion, hate literature, and terrorist glorification is on the agenda of NAP, however, due to lack of actions to limit activities of extremist group they have not be successful. These proscribed outfits can still use Twitter, Facebook, and many other social media accounts in addition to their blogs and websites to reach general public and their followers with their messages. The success achieved through NAP is laudable, but still it has not created a better image for Pakistan internationally. This brings our discussion about the role of communication in image creation.

b. Role of Communication in image creation

Strategic communication popularity as a science started in the second decade of this century (Van Ruler, 2018). Initially the concept was mainly used for the military and national governments communications programs (Holtzhusen & Zerfass, 2014). They further argue that with the evolution of the concept it is now considered as an umbrella concept that can be employed in range of activities may it be health communication or perception management. According to them this concept is not a substitution to any pervious concept of communication sciences. This is a concept that can offer complementary insights to pave way for interdisciplinary research. It is important to study this field because today's problems are different than the traditional communication activities and changes in technology is making it hard to distinguish among many kinds of communication (Hallahn et al, 2007). This concept is also important because in today's dynamic world every organization prefer to communication directly with their stakeholders (Van Ruler, 2018).

The focus of strategic communication for image creation must not only be on the process but also on

the action or practice of stakeholders particularly the public. However, this conception of communication was missing the public sphere, then it was added to the definition (Holtzhusen & Zerfass, 2014). The conception of public sphere has changed after the popularity of social media (Abdulhamid et al, 2021). The penetration of Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, and other social media platform has marginalized the role of major public media. The contemporary public sphere is more participative compared to 20th century. Previously, it was the old media that would represent the viewpoints of the society however, now new media allows the public to directly take part in any public debate without any hurdles. In the past the public sphere belonged to a very selected class the well-connected and aristocratic people (Holtzhusen & Zerfass, 2014). With the evolution of social media, the sphere is now more open to a variety of classes (Shahzad & Siraj, 2020). Making it easy to create or tarnish image of an organization or even a country, this technique is academically referred as media framing. The following section explains how media framing is practice by powerful media houses in creating desired perceptions.

c. Media Framing

Ospina Estupinan (2017) claims that various surveys and researchers have indicated that there is a correlation between media coverage and public perception. The media controls a nation's image through media framing to shape international preferences. Media framing is a method to analyze how media defines issues of public interest (Ali, Jan & Saleem, 2013). Goffman defined media framing as the principles of organization, which govern social events (Persson, 2018) Frames are the lenses through which social reality is viewed (Dillard, Solomon & Samp, 1996). It is through these frames that people view the reality either that reality is grounded or not, whether it reflects the facts and figures or not does not matter to the public. If it's viral on social media, it is true to them.

Chari (2013) explains that media framing is the process of showing events occurring in the world to the general public. The events are shown in a manner to achieve a certain goal or objective. The manner in which these events are shown creates a penetrating image on the audience's minds, that would have a

lasting effect and not easy to change (Ninan, Mahalingam & Clegg, 2022). This procedure of media framing can be biased because of the subjectivity of the gate keepers involved and the gate keepers always have a motive may it be covert or overt. Furthermore, each gate keeper interprets and edits the news according to one's own judgment and agenda (Connolly and Piper, 2022). This subjectivity and biasness are what puts positive or negative in the minds of the general public and creates a perception that it is difficult to change or even discuss in some cases (Elsdon-Baker, 2015).

Powell (2018) gives one the best examples of media framing happened in post 9/11 era where the media houses used a thematic framing technique. In this technique the reporting of terrorism committed by a Muslim was reported differently by acts of terror committed by non-Muslims. Paradoxically, this way of media framing helped the terrorists more than getting the truth out as it created more fear for public than raising the pertinent issues attached to terrorism. As media framing gets accepted by public and it grows it will ultimately even influence the political discourse of countries (Powell, 2018). As it happened in case of Pakistan where the US discourse for Pakistan was fixated at "Do more!" because of media framing despite the fact the country lost more in terrorism than any other country.

Powell concludes that Muslims media framing as radicals has increase since 9/11 and it has consequences how publics and countries perceive the Muslims or the Muslims countries such as Pakistan. He further asserts that the supremacy of the U.S. media worldwide adds to the power of this framing that influences global relations with Islamic countries like Pakistan (Powell, 2018).

This discussion implies that it is imperative to know how Pakistan is viewed by leading media houses.

Method

The purpose of this research is to determine that whether Pakistan is seen as a victim or perpetrator of terrorism in the three most widely read magazines around the world such as: Newsweek, Time and the Economist (Li and Zhang, 2022). For this study, a total of 12 articles purely related to depicting the image of Pakistan were selected from their online sources. The period selected for this study was from

2014-2016 because of the initiation of the military operation Zarb-e-Azb. All the articles from the magazines were published during the same tenure.

A content analysis of the 12 articles was carried out to achieve the objective of this research. Content analysis is a research technique for the objective, systematic and quantitative description of the manifest content of communication (Berelson, 1952). Communication is the only way in which living beings can understand each other and analyzing the content of communication has proved to provide useful insights regarding the subject of study (Kim and So, 2022). Communication, when used and carried out by media, can be biased because of "Gate keeping." Gate keeping is the process of selecting and editing of any news items according to personal observations. Gate

keepers can be anyone who is related to the selection and editing of news items, that is, reporters, editors, producers or even anchors. These observations were kept in mind while doing the content analysis.

II. Data Analysis

The selected articles were thoroughly studied, and relevant data was extracted. The data was analyzed in a spreadsheet program to generate the quantitative findings of this qualitative study.

The data was entered in the spreadsheet program in two columns, one showing Pakistan as a victim of terrorism and the other showing Pakistan as a perpetrator of terrorism. Then the frequencies of both the categories were calculated. The frequencies of the data analyzed are shown in the table and graph below:

	Frequency
Pakistan as a victim of terrorism	42%
Pakistan as a perpetrator of terrorism	58%

Table 1

Figure 1

III. Discussion

The data analysis of the content from the world's three leading magazines shows that the Islamic Republic of Pakistan, despite fighting the war against terrorism and losing so much is still considered to be a perpetrator of terrorism. Results show that 58% of the content of articles in the magazines depicts

Pakistan as a country that instigates the act of terrorism and is playing a vital role in spreading it. Only 42% of the data shows that Pakistan is a victim of terrorism. As discussed by Wahab (2021) one factor for not winning the media war is because of the weak role of Pakistani media houses that have failed to create a success story for Pakistan's war against

terrorism. As argued by Khan and Saeed (2018) the extremists were more efficient to use social media to their benefit compared to the government. Such groups were able to use Twitter, Facebook, and many other social media accounts in addition to their blogs and websites to reach general public and their followers with their messages. On the other hand, the government had very little presence in this arena.

Beside that the government could not put forward the narrative that after joining the West's war on terrorism Pakistan suffered the most from the terrorist activities. They faced not only losses in terms of human casualties but also economically and socially. While Pakistan was busy fighting the terrorism its neighbors may it be India and Bangladesh were busy attracting foreign direct investment from west and increasing their growth. While we were busy fighting the West's war on terrorism, they were busy investing in India and Bangladesh. Pakistan also had to pay the social cost for this war when hundreds of our youth left their homes and education to join militias on the false pretext of glory and heroism.

The government could have broadened their case on arguments that Pakistan is experiencing violence in different shapes and forms may it be suicide attacks on public places, bombing on target places, or ethnic conflicts in Balochistan and Karachi. But due to wrong priorities and the inactions of stakeholders we have created an image where instead of being the victim Pakistan is portrayed as an instigator of terrorism. The media houses in Pakistan could counter this by telling the world that one of the leading factors for terrorist activities in Pakistan was due to the porous nature border with Afghanistan. Beside that the world must not forget that Pakistan is giving shelter to millions of Afghan refugees and these militants blend in them to escape the eyes of law enforcing agencies. One of the major factors in winning any war is the intelligence that the law enforcing agencies gather from the public but when such militants blend in them it is impossible for the government to get correct intelligence. With all these shortcomings still, Pakistan had their share of success in this West's war on terrorism, and we have to highlight those.

The success of Karachi operation must be put forward, the city was on the brink of failure but after the operation things changed dramatically for the people.

Secondly, FATA region merger in Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa is another milestone in the war against terrorism. The region due to its remoteness and underdevelopment was an easy target for terrorist outfits but after the merger things are changing for good in the region. Finally, substantial actions have been taken to restrain terror financing in the country, and we have promoted all these success stories.

It is pertinent to discuss that Pakistan have employed a range of intervention to tackle terrorism promotion, hate literature, and terrorist glorification, however, due to lack of continuity in policies and good governance the country has not be successful. Because of this many proscribed outfits can still use Twitter, Facebook, and many other social media accounts in addition to their blogs and websites to reach general public and their followers with their messages (Khan and Saeed 2018). The success achieved through NAP is laudable, but still it has not created a better image for Pakistan internationally because of ineffective media framing and lack of proper communication by the state.

IV. Conclusion and Recommendations

From the results it can be concluded that there is a negative opinion regarding the role of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan against terrorism. In international media Pakistan is being portrayed as a committer and perpetrator of terrorism. Most of the data analyzed is against the efforts that Pakistan has put in against the War on Terrorism. The results show that even though Pakistan has been playing the role of an ally in the war against terrorism. Despite the negative image that has been created by international media there are some areas where Pakistan is considered as a victim of terrorism. Results show that in media there are some groups that argue that Pakistan has been dragged in this war on terrorism and has no direct part in the upbringing of this menace. As Powell highlights media houses used a thematic framing technique by reporting of terrorism committed by a Muslim differently than a non-Muslim. Paradoxically, this media framing helped the terrorists more in Pakistan than getting the truth out as it created more fear for public then raising the pertinent issues attached to terrorism in Pakistan. As it happened in case of Pakistan where the US discourse for Pakistan was fixated at "Do more!"

because of media framing despite the fact the country lost more in terrorism than any other country. Based on the discussion and conclusion this study proposes the following recommendation. First, the government of Pakistan must engage some important lobbyist in the West that must tell the story of Pakistan to the world and highlights the sacrifices that were made by our forces in ensuring peace in the country. Apart from this the state must partner with the local media houses to create a positive image of the country among the public. We need to educate the local population how vital their contribution in achieving and sustaining peace in the country. Finally, the government must ensure through novel ideas to manage the use of social media among the public and also educate them how to use it in responsible ways. This study is important because of its novelty and bringing in a new area to the view of the public and policy makers. There is a need by the policy makers to take up this matter to the highest forums and bring in a change regarding the image of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan as a culprit in the war on terror. The study can be further explored by studying other types of print and electronic media. The time period for the study can also be lengthened to find out more insightful results regarding the image of Pakistan. The present study was constrained by time and cost, but it can reveal more useful information if conducted without such constraints.

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